

Critical Review of Bailyn (2003)

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Abstract. Bailyn (2003) discusses local-scrambling involving A-properties and long-distance scrambling involving A'-properties. Local scrambling is driven by the [D] feature on the head of IP and long-distance scrambling is triggered by a discourse-related [OP] feature. He then proposes a derivational system to describe the two types of scrambling without the reference to A and A'-properties. However, I criticise that the feature-driven analysis cannot capture the position of verbs regarding the adverb test in Russian OVS and the interpretive and formal license of Russian OVS order. By contrast, interface-based flexible-style analyses can, which assume some orders can be base-generated and make reference to the PF (phonological form) interface (Titov, 2021).

Keywords: syntax; Russian; local-scrambling; long-distance scrambling

1 Critical Review

Bailyn argues that long-distance scrambling involves A'-properties, which does not change binding relations.

(1) No binding effects

a.

Ja xoču, čtoby studenty_i pročitali [knigi drug o druge_i]
I want that students read books-Acc about each other
'I want the students to read the books about each other.'

b.

[Knigi drug o druge_i]_k ja xoču, čtoby studenty_i pročitali t_k
books about each other I want that students read

Figure 1: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 43.*

A'-scrambling triggers weak crossover violations in (2b), when an object is scrambled over a coreferent pronoun. This is analogous to quantifier raising in (2a). This suggests again the A'-scrambled object reconstructs to its base position.

(2) Weak Crossover

- a. *Ja xoču, čtoby ee sobaka poljubila každuju devočku
 I want that [its_i dog]-NOM loves [every girl]_i-ACC t_i
 *'I want her dog to love every girl.'
- ' b. *Každuju devočku ja xoču, čtoby ee sobaka poljubila
 [every girl]_i-ACC I want that [its_i dog]-NOM loves t_i
 *'I want her dog to love every girl.'

Figure 2: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 44.*

Bailyn assumes Russian long-distance scrambling is discourse-driven triggered by the operator type feature of a functional category (Kitahara, 1997; Kawamura, 2001), making it semantically vacuous only with regard to binding effects but directly relevant for discourse interpretation. Conversely, local-scrambling exhibits A-properties. A-movement (subjecthood) tests show that all constructions in issue feed new binding relations and do not feed weak crossover violations.

The changes in binding relations can be tested using Principle A of the binding theory. In Figures 3-7, b sentences all permit the inverted constituent to bind an anaphor that it did not c-command before the movement.

(3)OVS

- a. *[Otagai-no_i sensei-ga] karera-o_i hihansita
 each other's teachers-Nom they-Acc criticized
 *'Each other's_i teachers criticized them_i.'
- b. ?Karera-o_i [otagai-no_i sensei]-ga t hihansita
 they-Acc each other's teacher-Nom criticized
 'They_i were criticized by each other's_i teachers.'

Figure 3: *Saito, 2003, p. 485.*

- (4) dative experiencers
- a. ???Svoja_i rabota nraivitsja Maše_i
[self's work]-Nom pleases Masha-Dat
'Masha likes her work.'
- b. Maše_i nraivitsja svoja_i rabota
Masha-Dat pleases [self's work]-Nom
'Masha likes her work.'

Figure 4: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 50*

- (5) possessive-PP inversion
- a. ???[Svoj_i dom] byl u Petrovyx_i
[self's house]-Nom was at the Petrovs
'The Petrovs had their own house.'
- b. U Petrovyx_i byl [svoj_i dom]
at the Petrovs was [self's house]-Nom
'The Petrovs had their own house.'

Figure 5: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 50*

- (6) iv. adversity impersonals
- a. *Puljami prinadlezaščimi drug drugu ranilo milicionerov
bullets-INSTR belonging each other-DAT wounded the police-ACC
'Bullets belonging to each other wounded the policemen.'
- b. Milicionerov ranilo puljami prinadlezaščimi drug drug
policemen-ACC wounded bullets-INSTR belonging each other-DAT
'The police were wounded by bullets belonging to each other.'

Figure 6: *Lavine & Freidin, 2002, p. 278.*

Similarly, a breach of Principle C occurs in Figures 7-11 when the inverted constituent binds an R expression that it did not previously c-command.

(7) i. OVS

- a. [Novye znakomye Ivana_i] predstavili ego_i predsedatelju
 new friends of Ivan. introduced him-Acc chairman-Dat
 'Ivan's_i new friends introduced him_i to the Chairman.'
- b. *Ego_i predstavili [novye znakomye Ivana_i] predsedatelju
 him introduced new friends of Ivan chairman-Dat
 *'He_i was introduced to the chairman by Ivan's_i new friends'

Figure 7: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 51.*

- (8) a. [Sluxi ob Ivane_i] volnujut ego_i.
 rumors-Nom about Ivan worry him-Acc
 'Rumors about Ivan_i worry him_i.'
- b. *Ego_i volnujut [sluxi ob Ivane_i]
 him-Acc worry rumors-Nom about Ivan
 *'He_i is worried by the rumors about Ivan_i.'
- c. [Ego_i znakomyx] volnujut [sluxi ob Ivane_i]
 [his friends]-Acc worry rumors about Ivan
 'His_i friends are worried by the rumors about Ivan_i.'

Figure 8: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 51.*

(9)

ii. Locative PP inversion

- a. [Znakomye Ivana_i] byli u nego_i doma.
 friends of Ivan were at him at home
 'Friends of Ivan's_i were at his_i house.'
- b. *U nego_i doma byli [znakomye Ivana_i].
 at him at home were friends-Nom of Ivan
 'At his_i house were friends of Ivan's_i.'

Figure 9: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 51.*

(10) iii. Possessive-PP inversion

- a. ?[Igruški Ivana_i] byli u nego_i.
toys-Nom of Ivana were at him ?
'Toys of Ivan_i he_i had.'
- b. *U nego_i byli [igruški Ivana_i].
at him were toys-Nom of Ivan
'*He_i had toys of Ivan's_i.'

Figure 10: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 52.*

(11) iv. Dative experiencers

- a. [Znakomye Ivana_i] nravjatsja emu_i.
friends-Nom of Ivana like him-Dat
'Friends of Ivan_i please him_i.' (cf '*He likes friends of Ivan.')
- b. *Emu_i nravjatsja [znakomye Ivana_i].
he-Dat like-pl friends-Nom of Ivan
'*He_i is liked by friends of Ivan_i.'

Figure 11: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 52.*

Moreover, local-scrambling does not trigger weak crossover violations.

- (12) a. *Ee_i sobaka ljubit každuju devočku_i.
[her dog]-NOM loves [every girl]-ACC
'Her_i dog loves every girl_i.'
- b. [Každuju devočku]_k ljubit ee sobaka t_k.
[every girl]_i-ACC loves [her_i dog]-NOM
'Every girl is loved by her dog.'

Figure 12: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 52.*

(13) locative inversion

- a. *[Ee uborščica] vošla [v každyju komnatu].
 its cleaning lady entered into every room
 'Its cleaning lady entered every room.'
- b. V každyju komnatu vošla [ee uborščica].
 into every room entered its cleaning lady
 'Into every room entered its cleaning lady.'

Figure 13: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 52.*

(14) possessive-PP inversion

- a. *[Ee_i sobaka] byla na rukax u [každyj devočki]_i
 its dog was on arms at every girl
 'Her dog was in every girl's arms.'
- b. ?U [každyj devočki]_i byla na rukax [ee_i sobaka]
 at every girl was in arms her dog-NOM
 'Every girl had her dog in her arms.'

Figure 14: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 53.*

(15) dative experiencers

- a. ??[Ee sobaka] nužna [každyj devočke]_i
 her dog-NOM needs every girl-DAT
 'Her_i dog is needed by every girl_i.'
- b. [Každyj devočke]_i nužna [ee sobaka]
 every girl-DAT needs her dog-NOM
 'Every girl_i needs her_i dog.'

Figure 15: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 53.*

Miyagawa (1997) suggests that local-scrambling is driven by the EPP. Languages that have V-to-I and morphological case marking allow the scrambling of objects due to the EPP. Bailyn extends EPP-analysis and unites all examples in Figures 3-4 and 16-22 as 'Generalised inversion'.

(16) Russian -EPP acct of Adversity Impersonals

Soldata ranilo pulej
soldier-Acc wounded bullet-Instr
'The soldier was wounded by a bullet.'

Figure 16: *Lavine & Freidin, 2002, p. 256.*

(17) Locative Inversion (LI):

a. V klasse pojavilsja noven'kij PP-V-S
in class appeared new (one)
'A new boy appeared in class.'

b. Na posadočnuju polosu prizemlilsja samolet.
onto -----runway----- landed airplane
'An airplane landed on the runway.'

Figure 17: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 48, citing Babyonyshev, 1996.*

(18) PP Inversion

a. U menja est' vopros. PP-V-S
at me is question-Nom
'I have a question.'

b. U nas rodilas' dočka PP-V-S
at us was born daughter-Nom
'A daughter was born to us'

Figure 18: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 48.*

(19) Dative experiencers

a. Saše nraŭjatsja deti
Sasha-Dat likes-pl children-Nom
'Sasha likes children.'

b. Soldatam vidna doroga
soldiers-Dat visible-fem sg road-Nom-f-sg
'The soldiers can see the road.'

Figure 19: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 49.*

(20)
 "Bad health" verbs
 Menja tošnit ot ryby O-V-PP
 me-Acc nauseates from fish
 'I feel sick from the fish.'

Figure 20: Preslar, 1998.

(21) OVS
 Étu knigu čitaet Ivan O-V-S
 [this book]-Acc reads Ivan
 'Ivan is reading this book.'

Figure 21: Bailyn, 2003, p. 49.

(22) a. the schema of Generalized Inversion

b. characteristics of IP-inversion

- Non-Nominative XP in SpecIP:
- V comes before the subject;
- Differs from (Standard) Topicalization (IP-adjunction)

Figure 22: Bailyn, 2003, p. 49.

Examples that have the properties in Figure 22b are analysed as resulting from EPP-driven movement into SpecIP, with V-raising over the Nominative subject. This results in the order O/PP V-S/ Dat-V-Nom.

Bailyn proposes that the EPP is triggered by the strong [D] feature on the head of IP.

Additionally, Russian IP-inversion is followed by V raising to I triggered by a finiteness feature, which can be satisfied by either V-to-I or by the raised Nominative subject in SVO.

Bailyn proposes a derivational approach to represent the two types of scrambling while eliminating references to A or A'-movement and removing the need for reconstruction as a separate phenomenon. He adopts assumptions about derivational approach from Saito (2003):

- i. Assume Copy Theory of Movement
- ii. Assume XP arguments exhibit (at least) these features:
[P] (PF-relevant)
[D], [OP] (LF-relevant)
- iii. Assume WH-movement and Long-Distance Scrambling are driven by [OP] feature
- iv. Assume the motivation for Inversion (A-scrambling) is D-feature

Figure 23: *Some assumptions under the derivational approach.*

Bailyn adopts the 'feature-splitting' approach, allowing him to propose a purely derivational approach to scrambling. NPs are associated with LF and PF features, but features can be split by movement (Saito, 2003). Bailyn argues that NPs are interpreted and enter into binding relations at any point in the derivation where their [D] features are active. In Figure 24a EPP-driven scrambling, the XP moves with the [D] feature and the phonological feature. Since the [D] feature moves, the XP that undergoes this operation is interpreted and enters into binding relations in the landing site. Therefore, when the [D] feature raises, the EPP-driven movement can satisfy Principle A in Figures 3-6 and violate Principle C in Figures 7-11.

However, in Figure 24b discourse-driven scrambling, XP moves with the phonological feature. This movement is driven by the [OP], and the D feature remains in the base position. This is where the NP enters into the binding relation, and where it is reconstructed.

- (24)
- a. EPP-driven scrambling: (local, A)
[_{IP}XP_i [D],[P] [r...t_i [∅],[P] ...]]
 - b. Discourse-driven Scrambling: (long, A')
[_{IP}XP_i [P],[OP] [IP...t_i [D],[P],[∅P] ...]]

Figure 24: *Bailyn, 2003, p. 57.*

Although this feature-driven analysis seems to account for the examples above, I argue that it is problematic. In Bailyn's analysis, local-scrambling is driven by D-feature on the head of IP. This approach aligns with the Universal Base Hypothesis, which assumes that SVO is the universal base order and all alternative orders are derived by movement (Zwart, 1997). Bailyn argues that to derive Russian OVS, the direct object moves out of VP into the SpecIP, and the verb undergoes V-to-I, crossing the Nominative subject. In Russian, the [+T] feature on I can be satisfied by either movement of the subject to SpecIP (resulting in SVO), or by V-to-I movement, in which case a non-subject moves to SpecIP to satisfy the EPP (resulting in OVS). In English, there is no V-to-I movement available, so

English lacks the OVS order. Therefore, the [+T] must be satisfied by movement of the subject to SpecIP.

However, V-to-I analysis is not supported by adverb placement tests (Titov, 2013). In both SVO and OVS in Russian, the adverb marking the left margin of the VP must precede the verb, clearly indicating that the verb remains within the VP (Titov, 2013).

- (25)
- a. Ja dumaju, čto Ivan často celuet Mašu
 I think that Ivan-NOM often kisses Masha-ACC
 'I think that Ivan often kisses Masha.'
- b. * Ja dumaju, čto Ivan celuet často Mašu
 I think that Ivan-NOM kisses often Masha-ACC

Figure 25: Titov, 2013, p. 38.

- (26)
- a. Ja dumaju, čto Mašu často celuet Ivan
 I think that Masha-ACC often kisses Ivan-NOM
 'I think that Ivan often kisses Masha.'
- b. * Ja dumaju, čto Mašu celuet často Ivan
 I think that Masha-ACC kisses often Ivan-NOM

Figure 26: Titov, 2013, p. 39.

Moreover, Bailyn suggests that A'-scrambling is driven by discourse-related requirements; however, A-scrambling is purely triggered by a strong [+D] feature on the head of IP. He adopts the analysis of generalized inversion from Bailyn (2004) where he assumes Russian OVS is as economical as SVO because of the same number of operations. He also suggests that all movements involved in generalized inversion do not achieve interpretive effects, including OVS. However, OVS is interpretively licensed. OVS can only be used when the object is IS (Information-Structurally) prominent and the subject is IS non-prominent (Titov, 2021). While OVS order is ungrammatical in Figure 28 where both arguments are prominent and in Figure 29 where both arguments are non-prominent, OVS is possible in Figure 30 where the object is prominent and the subject is non-prominent.

- (28) [What did the children do to the toy?]_{CONTEXT}
- a. # Igrušku [SLOMALI]_{FOC} deti OVS
 toy.ACC broke children
- b. Deti [SLOMALI]_{FOC} igrušku SVO
 children broke toy.ACC
 'The children broke the toy.'

Figure 28: Titov, 2021, p. 9.

- (29) [What happened?]_{CONTEXT}
 a. # [Igrušku slomali DETI]_{FOC} OVS
 toy.ACC broke children
 b. [Deti slomali IGRUŠKU]_{FOC} SVO
 children broke toy.ACC
 ‘The children broke the toy.’

Figure 29: Titov, 2021, p. 9.

- (30) [Who broke the/a toy?]_{CONTEXT}
 Igrušku slomali [DETI]_{FOC} OVS
 toy.ACC broke children
 ‘The/a toy was broken by (the) children.’

Figure 30: Titov, 2021, p. 8.

Furthermore, Bailyn’s account fails to explain the formal license of Russian OVS. In this account, OVS can be derived by A-scrambling an object to SpecIP above the subject and should not rely on whether the object carries an accusative morphological case marker or not. It is not enough to say that OVS is possible in a language that has morphological cases, and therefore allows V-to-I. Even in such a language, OVS may not be possible if the object does not carry an accusative case marker in Figure 31 because the thematic relation is not formally represented. Only SVO interpretation is possible because this is represented by syntax: the agent is syntactically higher than the patient (Titov, 2013).

- (31) [What’s new with mother?]_{CONTEXT}
 Mat’ NAVESTILA DOČ’ SVO/*OVS
 mother-NOM/ACC visited daughter-NOM/ACC
 ‘Mother visited daughter.’
 ‘*Daughter visited mother.’

Figure 31: Titov, 2013, p. 46.

OVS is possible when the formal license is applied which means the thematic relations are morphologically recovered at PF (Titov, 2013).

- (32) [What’s new with mum?]_{CONTEXT}
 Mamu NAVESTILA DOČ’ OVS
 mum-ACC visited daughter-NOM/ACC
 ‘Daughter visited mum.’

Figure 32: Titov, 2013, p. 46.

There is an alternative interface-based analysis which allows to base-generate OVS (Titov, 2013). The

object is base-generated above the subject within VP and undergoes A-movement to SpecIP. Thus, the problem of ordering the subject and the verb in OVS disappears because it allows the verb to merge with the subject first. Under this analysis, OVS involves an inverse order of theta-role assignment, and is syntactically more costly (Titov, 2013).

Therefore, OVS requires an interpretative license. OVS is used if it maps transparently onto the discourse template in Figure 33 as in Figure 30 (Titov, 2012).

(33) Information Structure
 ARGUMENT ARGUMENT
 [+IS-prominent] >> [-IS-prominent]

Figure 33: Titov, 2013, p. 36.

Additionally, whenever scrambling representation is mapped on to PF, PF detects the inverse order of theta-role assignment and it needs to recover the thematic prominence relations in its own representation via inflectional morphology (e.g. m-case assignment algorithms) in Figure 32 (Titov, 2013).

2 Conclusion

In conclusion, Bailyn proposes a derivational approach to represent local-scrambling and long-distance scrambling. While local-scrambling is to satisfy the [D] feature on the head of IP, long-distance scrambling is driven by discourse-related [OP]. I criticize the feature-driven analysis on the basis of Russian examples: the position of verbs regarding the adverb in OVS and the interpretive and formal license of OVS. These issues are all accounted for in the interface-based analysis.

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